

Species composition of *Nephotettix* in Tamil Nadu

S. Vennila and P. C. Sundara Babu. Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, India

We collected *Nephotettix* specimens from 12 rice-growing centers in Tamil Nadu: Kancheepuram, Tirur, Vellore, Cuddalore, Tiruchirappalli, Aduthurai, Madurai, Ambasamudram, Nagercoil, Paiyur, Coimbatore, and Bhavanisagar.

Specimens were separated on the basis of morphological characters and sent to IIRI for identification.

Two additional species besides those already identified — *N. virescens* (Distant) and *N. nigropictus* (Stål) — were found (see table). For the additional species *N. malayanus* Ishihara and Kawase and *N. modulatus* Melichar, only females were found. Previous records of *N. malayanus* in India are available from Calcutta and Malabar Coast. *N. modulatus*, an

African and Malagasian species, is reported for the first time in Asia.

All four species were recorded at Coimbatore only. *N. virescens* was found at all sites and was the only species at Cuddalore, Tiruchirappalli, and Nagercoil. *N. virescens* dominated in all places. When *N. nigropictus* was recorded, it was next to *N. virescens*. *N. nigropictus* was found in seven places, *N. malayanus* in two, and *N. modulatus* in six. □

Nephotettix species in different regions of Tamil Nadu, India.

Locality	<i>Nephotettix</i> spp. (no.)	Species composition ^a							
		<i>N. virescens</i>		<i>N. nigropictus</i>		<i>N. malayanus</i>		<i>N. modulatus</i>	
		no.	%	no.	%	no.	%	no.	%
Kancheepuram	74	73	98.65	—	—	—	—	1	1.35
Tirur	204	196	96.08	4	1.96	—	—	4	1.96
Vellore	110	85	77.27	17	15.45	—	—	8	7.28
Cuddalore	44	44	100.00	—	—	—	—	—	—
Tiruchirappalli	233	233	100.00	—	—	—	—	—	—
Aduthurai	189	177	93.65	—	—	2	1.06	10	5.29
Madurai	278	231	83.09	47	16.91	—	—	—	—
Ambasamudram	25	23	92.00	2	8.00	—	—	—	—
Nagercoil	31	31	100.00	—	—	—	—	—	—
Paiyur	32	28	87.50	4	12.50	—	—	—	—
Coimbatore	144	109	75.71	19	13.19	4	2.77	12	8.33
Bhavanisagar	29	23	79.31	4	13.79	—	—	2	6.90

^a — = not found.

New genetic makeup of brown planthopper (BPH) populations in Central Java, Indonesia

K. Sogawa, Soekirno, and Y. Raksadinata. Indonesia-Japan Joint Programme on Food Crop Protection, Directorate of Food Crop Protection, P. O. Box 36, Pasarminggu, Jakarta, Indonesia

BPH populations had been below the economic injury level on IR36 and Cisadane until recently. However, BPH populations which started to infest Cisadane in Yogyakarta in 1985 became prevalent in Central Java this year. Development of populations that could break down Cisadane resistance was closely related to the spread of new high-yielding national varieties Krueng Aceh and Sadang, whose genetic resistance to the BPH is rather vulnerable.

1. Honeydew excreted by adult females of Yogyakarta and Jatisari populations of the BPH on selected rice varieties. Mean and 95% confidential ranges are indicated by spot and bar, respectively.